

Kinetic and Mechanistic Study of Oxidation of 3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones by Pyridinium Fluorochromate

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Kinetics of oxidation of 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one and its aryl substituted counterparts by pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) in aquo-acetic acid-sulphuric acid medium, have been studied at four different temperatures. Activation parameters have been computed. The reaction rate is found to be acid-dependent in the concentration range 0.47–0.94 M. The rates of oxidations show first order kinetics each in [Piperidone], [PFC] and $[H^+]$. The rates increase with an increase in the acetic acid composition, while remain almost unaffected with an increase in ionic strength of the medium. A tentative mechanism has been proposed and the rate law deduced.

Most of the 3-alkyl substituted 2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones have been investigated on the mechanistic aspects of their oxidations¹, but there is very little information on the mechanistic aspects of aryl substituted piperidone oxidations. Hence we thought it worthwhile to investigate the kinetics of oxidation of 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenyl-, 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-di-*o*-tolyl-, 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-di-*p*-tolyl-, 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-di-*o*-anisyl-, 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-di-*p*-anisyl- and 3,5-dimethyl-2,6 di-*o*-chlorophenylpiperidin-4-one in aquo-acetic acid-sulphuric acid medium under varying conditions.

Results and Discussion

Results of the study are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

$[H_2SO_4]$, the rates increased with increase in [substrate], with first order kinetics in [substrate]. The variation in $[H^+]$ at fixed [substrate] and [PFC] had a positive effect with first order kinetics in $[H^+]$.

The rates increased with increase in acetic acid content in the solvent indicating ion-dipole interaction. Added sodium sulphate had no significant effect on the rates of oxidations.

The rates of oxidation were measured at four different temperatures and the rate constants were calculated. The activation parameters corresponding to these rate constants have also been computed from the Arrhenius plots (Table 2).

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR THE OXIDATION OF 3,5-DIMETHYL-2,6-DIARYL-SUBSTITUTED-PIPERIDIN-4-ONES BY PFC IN AQUO-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) AT 323 K

[PFC] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [P] mol dm ⁻³	[H ₂ SO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ *	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ *	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ *	k_{obs} (10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)
0.50	2.0	6.25	4.03	3.27	2.49	3.75	3.45	1.09	
0.75	2.0	6.25	3.18	2.65	2.05	3.10	2.70	0.89	
1.0	2.0	6.25	2.62	2.06	1.74	2.55	2.16	0.73	
1.25	2.0	6.25	—	1.82	1.38	1.79	—	0.62	
1.5	2.0	6.25	2.23	—	—	—	1.89	—	
1.0	1.75	6.25	2.34	1.78	1.69	2.27	1.88	0.58	
1.0	2.0	6.25	2.62	2.06	1.74	2.55	2.16	0.73	
1.0	2.25	6.25	3.00	2.40	1.94	2.79	2.49	0.79	
1.0	2.5	6.25	3.18	2.66	2.45	2.92	3.02	0.88	
1.0	2.0	4.70	2.22	1.70	1.42	1.82	1.74	0.69	
1.0	2.0	6.25	2.62	2.06	1.74	2.55	2.16	0.73	
1.0	2.0	7.80	3.19	2.64	2.07	2.87	2.71	0.98	
1.0	2.0	9.40	3.54	3.15	2.35	3.13	3.37	1.28	

*At 328 K.

At fixed $[H_2SO_4]$ with ten-fold excess of substrate, the first order plots $\log [PFC]$ vs time were linear up to one half-life, and the pseudo-first order rate constants computed were found to decrease with increasing [PFC]. At constant [PFC] and

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF 3,5-DIMETHYL-2,6-DIARYL-SUBSTITUTED-PIPERIDONES BY PFC AT 323 K

Piperidone	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	73.8	71.2	-56.9	89.3
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	81.8	79.1	-32.2	89.4
Phenyl	89.1	86.5	-11.8	90.2
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	93.5	90.9	+1.13	90.5
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	68.5	65.9	-77.5	90.6
<i>o</i> -Anisyl	96.5	93.9	-4.1	94.6

The absence of polymer formation when the reaction was conducted in the presence of acrylonitrile monomer indicated the non-involvement of the intermediate free radicals. The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by treating the substrate with excess oxidant. It was found to be 1 : 1 and the product isolated and characterised by usual spectral data was ascertained to be acylon.

Mechanism: It is evident from the literature² that the oxidations of ketones occur via enols if they are acid-catalysed reactions. It is also understood that two-electron oxidants attack the enol form rather than the keto form. This is the case for oxidation with PFC. Our previous study on the

oxidation of *N*-methyl-3-alkyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones also supports the above view. Based on the kinetic results, stoichiometry and product analysis it is appropriate to conclude that the enolisation is the first and fast step of oxidation. The subsequent rate-controlling step involves a concerted addition of PFC to enol and the resulting intermediate gives the product acyloin by rapid hydrolysis. Thus the elucidated mechanism shown in Scheme 1 is in accordance with the rate law,

$$-\frac{d[\text{PFC}]}{dt} = \frac{k_2 k_1}{k_{-1}} [\text{substrate}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{PFC}]$$

Scheme 1

Relative rates and substituent effects: The reactivity of various substituted 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diaryl-piperidin-4-ones conforms to the following order: *o*-chlorophenyl ($k_{\text{obs}} = 1.43 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) > *p*-anisyl ($k_{\text{obs}} = 1.39 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) > phenyl ($k_{\text{obs}} = 1.01 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) > *p*-tolyl ($k_{\text{obs}} = 0.90 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) \approx *o*-tolyl ($k_{\text{obs}} = 0.89 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) > *o*-anisyl ($k_{\text{obs}} = 0.19 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The electrostatic attraction existing between the non-bonding pair of electrons on the chlorine atom and the positive centre in the transition state stabilises the transition state and hence the enhanced rate in the *o*-chlorophenyl substituted piperidone. The kinetics of 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-di-*p*-chlorophenyl-piperidin-4-one could not be investigated due to solubility problem. The *p*-anisylpiperidone being richer in electron density by mesomeric effect, stabilises the transition state as in the case of *o*-chloro-

phenyl substituent. The lowest value of the rate constant found in *o*-anisylpiperidone may be due to the shifting off the OCH_3 group from the plane. In the case of *o*-tolyl- and *p*-tolylpiperidones electrostatic stabilisation is not operative and hence the rates of oxidations are comparable with that of the corresponding phenyl substituted piperidone.

Experimental

The substituted piperidin-4-ones were prepared by literature procedures⁵. Pyridinium fluorochromate (m.p. 107–09°) was prepared by the reported

method⁴. Acetic acid (A.R.) unaffected by chromic acid was used as solvent.

Kinetic experiments were carried out titrimetrically. The course of the reaction was followed by estimating the unconsumed PFC iodometrically. The concentration of the piperidone was always maintained high so that the pseudo-first order rate law could be applied. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated by the method of least squares.

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References

1. K. SELVARAJ, V. P. SENTHILNATHAN and K. RAMALINGAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 17, 589; M. KRISHNAPILLAY and A. THIRUNAVUKKARASU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 583; K. SELVARAJ and K. RAMALINGAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, 23, 388; KR. MEENAL and P. ROOPAKALYANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 624; K. SELVARAJ, S. SANKARAN, B. PREMA and K. RAMARAJAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 723.
2. J. S. LITTLER and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 827.
3. V. BALIAH and C. R. NOLLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3853.
4. M. N. BHATTACHARJEE, M. K. CHAUDHURI, H. S. DASGUPTA and N. ROY, *Synthesis*, 1982, 588.